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What Swiss In-Company Trainers Want: Needs, Interests, and Availability for Continuing Education

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Abstract

Being in-company trainer in a dual VET system is not only about imparting trade-related knowledge or know-how, but also about taking on a pedagogical role. However, this latter role is often neglected, as in-company trainers experience a strong pressure to be productive workers at the same time as they train apprentices. They also have a complex function with several hats. Accordingly, our study looked at their needs and preferences in terms of pedagogical continuing education offerings. Specifically, through an online survey, we asked in-company trainers from all over Switzerland (N=5'079) which continuing education offers would be most relevant for them, as well as the formats, modalities and periods of these courses. Comparisons by socio-demographic variables (such as company size, activity sector or geographical region) were then made to identify specific preferences. Our results should on the one hand better understand the situation and constraints of in-company trainers and, on the second hand, contribute to the development of course offerings that are closer to in-company trainers' needs.

Keywords

in-company trainers, continuing education, Swiss VET system

1 Theoretical framework

Lifelong learning (LLL) is promoted as a central element for the economic, cultural and social development, and is even formalized in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs; Comyn, 2018). This is also true in the context of VET (Cedefop, 2020), the training pathway undertaken by 2/3 of young people in Switzerland after compulsory school (Federal Statistical Office, 2022).

In view of this training system's importance in the Swiss landscape, it is relevant to look at the access to continuing education – which is part of LLL – for the persons in charge of training apprentices. On the one hand, VET teachers, whose role is by definition pedagogical, professionalise themselves by attending a quite long pedagogical training (between 600 and 1'800 hours), and regular continuing education courses (Perrenoud, 1994). On the other hand, in-company trainers, who receive short training to the function (40 hours), and whose

implication in the continuing education is largely underestimated. However, their role in training to an occupation is rather central, especially in the context of dual vocational education and training.

1.1 Roles and challenges of in-company trainers in a dual VET context

In-company trainers reflect a complex and fascinating actor in the VET landscape: they are workers, but at the same time they are also pedagogical figures for apprentices. They must therefore be productive, while at the same time finding time to pass on the knowledge of an occupation. This double role means – among others – that in-company trainers experience several challenges linked to their function, such as training apprentices when they have not actively chosen to be trainers, or finding the time needed for training in a context where their activity is rarely set up for this purpose (Baumeler & Lamamra, 2019). Therefore, having access to continuing education is an additional challenge, with characteristics specific to this function.

1.2 In-company trainers and continuing education

As a 2010 Cedefop report illustrates, in-company trainers do not have such easy access to continuing education and, where they do, it is mainly job-related training. In other words, in-company trainers' opportunities for lifelong learning are limited, partly because of their 'hybrid' status (Cedefop, 2010). Indeed, they simultaneously occupy the roles of trainer for apprentices, but also of worker, having to comply with the constraints of labour market. These constraints are quite high in dual VET, due to one specific issue characterizing it, that is the tension between two logics: producing and training (Moreau, 2003). As a result, in-company trainers are seen primarily as workers responding to a production logic and less - if at all - as figures playing a pedagogical role in the VET system (Lamamra et al., 2019). They can at most be recognized as key persons in the professional socialisation of apprentices, but more rarely as pedagogues. Their pedagogical role should however be more highly valued and recognised, in particular through access to continuous education not solely focused on their occupation (Lamamra et al., 2019). In this context, a study has been carried out to identify the needs and interests of in-company trainers in terms of continuing education (in particular, course content, preferred methods and formats, etc.), with a view to developing a targeted course offering.

1.3 Research questions

The study was based on the following research questions:

- Which continuing education courses are relevant for in-company trainers?
- What differences are there among in-company trainers in terms of their sociodemographic characteristics?

2 The study

The content of the survey followed an initial study, first carried out in the German-speaking part of Switzerland and then supplemented by data from the French- and Italian-speaking parts of Switzerland, where interviews on the subject of continuing education has made it possible to identify salient themes (Wenger & Lamamra, 2022).

In addition, an online survey was sent – via professional associations and through all Swiss cantons – to in-company trainers and to owners of training companies. A total of 5'079 people completed the survey ($M_{\text{age}}=41.13$ years; $SD=11.54$ years; 55.5% of women), which included questions on possible topics for the continuing education of in-company trainers, their format and modality, the periods of the day and year for carrying them out, etc. Sociodemographic questions were also included in the questionnaire (e.g., company size or activity sector, Table

1). Participation was voluntary, and responses to the survey were guaranteed to be anonymous and confidential.

Table 1

Respondents' distribution in terms of sociodemographic information

Respondents' distribution (N = 5'079)								
Sex	Women 55.5%		Men 42.7%		Does not wish to answer 1.8%			
Linguistic Area	German-speaking Switzerland 83.7%		French-speaking Switzerland 15.7%		Italian-speaking Switzerland 0.6%			
Activity Rate	Part-time (less than 50%) 2.7%		Part-time (50%-89%) 24.0%		Full-time (more than 90%) 73.3%			
Company Size	Micro (less than 10 employees) 17.9%		Small (10-49 employees) 34.3%		Medium (50-249 employees) 25.6%		Big (more than 250 employees) 22.2%	
Function	Employee with in-company trainer function (40 hour-course completed) 64.1%		Employee with in-company trainer function (40 hour-course not yet completed) 12.3%		Company owner with in-company trainer function 17.5%		Company owner without in-company trainer function 6.0%	
Swiss Region	Leman's Lake 7.8%	Mittelland 38.1%	North-West 4.0%	Zürich 2.9%	East 36.5%	Central 10.3%	Tessin 0.5%	
Activity Sector	Agricult. 3%	Industry 11.5%	IT & Tech 8.2%	Construction 16.6%	Trade 6.4%	Hotel-restaurant 6.7%	Managem. & Admin 20.3%	Health & Education 25.8%

Findings

To answer the first research question, that is with regard to the continuing education offers that appear to be relevant to in-company trainers, the most popular were those concerning the *roles of in-company trainers, their tasks and challenges* (chosen by 64.4% of respondents), *knowledge of the adolescent public* (55.9% of respondents) and the *relational and communication skills of in-company trainers* (49.8%; Figure 1). This same “top three” was also found in another question that asked for a ranking of the different continuing education offers. Hence, these results highlight the salience to in-company trainers of their roles in the dual VET system, the relational aspect with apprentices and the issues directly related to the latter. Moreover, the problematic of the *roles, tasks and challenges* of in-company trainers reflects the complexity of the function, which is often not even explicitly clarified in the bill of specifications. In

addition, interest in continuing education on in-company trainers' roles, tasks and challenges underlines the tension between producing and training that is characteristic of their function (Lamamra et al., 2019). The relational dimension of the function, which includes not only transmission of knowledge and know-how, but also support, is reflected in the choice of training courses on *relational and communication skills* and *knowledge of the adolescent public*. This result highlights the relational dimension of the function, central in accompanying and socializing apprentices, as in offering them conditions for successfully achieving their training (Berger et al., 2019; Masdonati & Lamamra, 2009). In this sense, the results illustrate a certain desire to gain greater recognition as a pedagogical figure, and not only as skilled worker, but also to "professionalise" in-company trainer's function (Wenger & Lamamra, 2022).

Another finding to be highlighted is that, in contrast to the trends identified by politics for the Swiss VET sector¹, in-company trainers have shown relatively little interest for training in *digital skills* (34.4% of respondents) or for intercultural challenges (28.4%) in their answers.

Figure 1

Continuing education offers chosen as relevant by in-company trainers. N.B. it was possible to select more than one answer

By carrying out more detailed analyses² according to several sociodemographic criteria (second research question), we notice that in-company trainers without a company owner's function³ selected the different continuing education offers to a greater extent (vs. company owners). This is reflected on the one hand in the number of training courses selected and on the other hand in the continuing education's duration desired. Also, the larger the size of the company, the more answers the respondents selected. This indicates a strong tie between the company's structure, its organisation regarding apprentices training, the position of in-company trainers within the company structure and the possibilities of participating to continuing education. Regarding Swiss geographical regions⁴, in-company trainers in the Lemman's Lake region were more interested in training on the roles, tasks and challenges of trainers and in pedagogical methods than

¹ See for example <https://www.sbf.admin.ch/sbf/fr/home/services/publications/base-de-donnees-des-publications/s-n-2019-1/s-n-2019-1c.html>.

² Chi-2 tests as well as ANOVAS were performed.

³ I.e., Both types of employees with in-company trainer function (40 hour-course completed or not).

⁴ See <https://www.admin.ch/gov/fr/accueil/documentation/communiqués.msg-id-10585.html>.

those in other regions. The Mittelland region indicated more interest than the other regions in training on time management, while the north-western Switzerland and the Zurich region stood out from the other regions for their interest in continuing education related to adolescents (communication skills, social and family issues, knowledge of the adolescent public). The analyses by geographical region thus reflect different needs in terms of continuing education, linked in particular to the various regional and cantonal organisations of courses to become in-company trainers, but also to different challenges in terms of economic environments, sectors, etc.

Other results reflect the preference of in-company trainers for face-to-face (vs. hybrid or distance learning) courses or exchanges of experience (Table 2). These choices seem to express their need to interact face-to-face and with peers, as their function often leads them to be isolated (especially in micro and small companies). Similar results have previously identified their need of interactions with peer regarding their initial training to the function (40hour-course) (Lamamra et al., 2019). Comparing these same results by professional sector, the results indicate that respondents in the construction, agriculture and industry sectors would particularly prefer the face-to-face format, while in other sectors such as IT or management and administration, the distance and hybrid formats are more strongly selected. This result reflects the diverse realities faced by in-company trainers in different activity sectors, some of whom are accustomed - even more so since the period of the covid-19 pandemic - to the distance and hybrid format, due in particular to the use of computers in their daily work.

When asked what the ideal organisation and duration of continuing education courses (in days per year) would be, in-company trainers seem to prefer full days or half days courses, and on average 2.5 days per year (almost one in three in-company trainers answered 2 days per year; Table 2). By comparing respondents by sociodemographic characteristics, we note for instance that individuals without a company owner's function would like to have longer training period than those with a company owner's function. Also, in-company trainers from medium and large companies, and those from the hotel, health and education sectors also indicate longer training periods. As for the preferred period, respondents with a company owner's function indicate evenings and weekends more than those without this function, which seems to be consistent with the different postures: an owner will indeed need to have her/his employees available during the day, while the latter prefer to keep their free time to themselves, without having to sacrifice it for continuous education.

Figure 2
Learning features for continuing education

Learning features (N = 5'079)				
Format	Face-to-face	Distance	Hybrid	
	76.3%	30.8%	24.0%	
Modality	Course	Exchange of experiences	Workshop	
	74.8%	55.5%	48.7%	
Organis.	Full days	Half days	Evenings	Weekends
	63.7%	58.6%	17.5%	4.2%
Duration	2 days/year	1 day/year	3 days/year	5 days/year
	28.3%	19.5%	18.8%	9.5%

3 Research significance

The study carried out with the aim of understanding the needs and preferences of in-company trainers in terms of continuing education first of all highlighted the contents, formats, methods and periods (including duration) generally favoured by this population (first research question). In addition, by comparing the respondents according to several sociodemographic criteria, the results provide more precise information about the predilections of each group (second research question). This is very important for continuing education organisers to consider when developing course offerings. Indeed, the aim is to offer 'à la carte' continuing education, as close as possible to in-company trainers' current needs in the field.

Beyond the results providing a clearer picture of the needs and interests of in-company trainers, the large number of respondents to the survey reflects several main issues for research in dual VET. First, this study highlights the need for in-company trainers to be able to benefit not only from updates related to their profession, but also - and even more importantly - from pedagogical further training courses. Second, these results underline the necessity to give these central actors in dual VET a visibility in research, but also in the governance of the system, which is mainly focused on apprentices or companies. Third, results show the need of recognition both for in-company trainers and for the tasks they are in charge of. Finally, different elements presented here go to the direction of a progressive professionalisation of the function, probably more expected by in-company trainers themselves, than by company owners. Indirectly, it also points out the limits of the Swiss "militia system" in the training of apprentices, with in-company trainers wanting more recognition and competence to take on their role.

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